

Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers

Emitter	CARS & ARES
Version	01
Revision	01

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Applicability of the document

These procedures apply to the ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing National Facilities and to the AERONET-ACTRIS associated photometer stations.

Acronyms

ACTRIS - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure

NF - National Facility

CARS - Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing

DC – Data Centre

MP – Mobile Platform

OP – Observational Platform

PI – Principal Investigator

ASP – Automatic Sun/sky/lunar Photometer

Reference documents

- [1]. Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments
- [2]. Guidelines for EARLINET-ACTRIS associated stations to access QA services
- [3]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms
- [4]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
- [5]. Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
- [6]. ACTRIS CIMEL Photometer Guide for Users

1 Introduction

Detailed instructions are provided for the deployment, operation, quality control, and calibration of **CIMEL photometers** within the **AERONET-ACTRIS network**, for both **stationary** and **mobile/marine sites**. Through **rigorous facility-based calibration, weekly local and remote QC, and network-level verification**, every CIMEL CE318T photometer remains a reliable and accurate instrument for climate research, atmospheric monitoring, and environmental policy applications. This Guide summarizes the main relevant information all users / instruments PI must be aware of.

The ACTRIS QA program ensures that all measurements meet the highest standards of accuracy and continuity. QA encompasses both **instrument performance verification** and **data validation**, bridging SOP execution and adherence to measurement guidelines.

2 Calibration Protocols

Calibration is performed in two phases: **post-field** (after deployment) and **pre-field** (before deployment) (Fig. 1). Both phases include **sun and sky calibrations**, with sky calibration conducted in the laboratory using **SI-traceable light sources** (Fig. 2). Depending on the CE318T version, sky calibration may also include **polarization characterization**.

Figure 1: Description of calibration protocol.

Figure 2: Radiometric calibration of a CIMEL CE318 by means of an SI-traceable light source.

At secondary calibration centers—**Observatoire de Haute-Provence (OHP, France)** and **Universidad de Valladolid (UVA, Spain)**—two reference instruments are always operated simultaneously.

Figure 3: OHP Sun intercalibration center

These instruments are calibrated quarterly at high-altitude reference sites, **Mauna Loa (Hawaii, NASA-AERONET)** and **Izaña (Tenerife, ASP-AEMET)**. All reference instruments are traceable to the PFR GAW standard AOD photometer, maintained by the Swiss ASP-PMOD within CARS, ensuring network-wide consistency of daytime AOD measurements. This traceability is documented in the calibration certificates issued by the relevant ASP units. An SI-traceable sun calibration in absolute irradiance is planned for the coming year.

Differences between post- and pre-field calibrations may necessitate **replacement or repair of filters, detectors, polarization components, or other optical elements**. Only after calibration and completion of any required adjustments are completed is the photometer considered ready for field deployment.

To minimize data gaps during calibration periods (typically around six weeks), thus maximizing the duty cycle, countries operating several ACTRIS/AERONET sites are advised to keep spare photometers for shared use, in close coordination with ASP. ASP-CNRS and ASP-UVA maintain a limited pool of such instruments.

3 Monitoring and data validation

To prevent drift and ensure data integrity:

- Site managers perform **weekly inspections** of the instrument's operation and data quality (see Table 1 in Document ASP-Standard Operating Procedures).
- Remote teams at ASP-CNRS (France) or ASP-UVA (Spain) provide parallel monitoring, analyzing trends and detecting anomalies (Fig. 4).
- No instrument remains in continuous operation for more than 18 months without recalibration, ensuring that slow, linear degradation remains a reasonable assumption.

Following post-field calibration, the data acquired over the observation period (12–18 months) are **reprocessed using linear interpolation between pre- and post-calibration constants**, maintaining continuity and preventing artificial jumps in the time series.

Table 1: Definition of level (AERONET definition)

Level	Description
Level 0	Raw, uncalibrated measurements directly from the instrument, no corrections or quality control.
Level 1.0	Calibrated and automatically processed data, with standard corrections (Rayleigh, pressure, ozone), but no cloud screening or QA/QC.
Level 1.5	Provisionally quality-assured data: automatic cloud screening and basic QA/QC applied. Still subject to residual uncertainties.
Level 2.0	Final quality-assured and manually verified data, with refined corrections. Reference level recommended for scientific analysis.

Note: While the above procedures primarily describe **stationary photometer sites**, mobile deployments—particularly marine photometers—follow the same SOP and QA principles but require adaptations for platform motion, environmental exposure, and mission-specific schedules.

Instrument [Site]	Category	Last Week	Last 24 hours	Weekly Data	Site Manager Information
#19 [IMAA_Potenza]	Robot Errors	28 Week, 28 Daily Max, 28 on 18:05:2018		View Data	Lucia Mona: mona@imaa.cnr.it Fabio Madonna: madonna@imaa.cnr.it Send Mail
#41 [AgiaMarina_Xyfiatou]	Robot Errors	45 Week, 18 Daily Max, 18 on 21:05:2018		View Data	Jean Sciare: j.sciare@cyi.ac.cy Send Mail
#43 [Ersa]	Robot Errors Temperature Jump Bad Temperature Reading	18 Week, 6 Daily Max, 6 on 21:05:2018 Last Occurred: 23:05:2018, 08:00:41 Last Occurred: 23:05:2018, 10:12:41		View Data	Gilles Azara: semaphorecapcorse@fr.oleane.com Send Mail
#44 [Capo_Verde]	Asymmetric Almucantars	49 Alm Groups, 11 Assym Alm Groups; Last Occurred: 24:05:2018, 18:56:01		View Data	Francisco Evora: francisco.evora@gmail.com Anaos Firon : anais.feron@lisa.u-pec.fr Send Mail
#72 [Carpentras]	Robot Errors	24 Week, 8 Daily Max, 8 on 24:05:2018		View Data	Thierry Podvin: thierry.podvin@univ-lille1.fr Send Mail
#75 [Ben_Salem]	InGaAs/Silicon Discrepancy	Avg Difference: 0.035188, Total: 219		View Data	Hassen Ayari: hassen.ayari@ird.fr Send Mail
#141 [El_Farafra]	Low Internal Battery	4.987564 Volts; Occurrences: 312		View Data	Mohamed Hussein Korany: m_korany2002@yahoo.com Send Mail
#166 [Mainz]	Robot Errors	33 Week, 13 Daily Max, 13 on 22:05:2018		View Data	Bjoern Nillius: b.nillius@mpic.de Send Mail

Figure 4: Example of parameter list to be checked for each instrument on a daily /weekly basis.

4 Additional resources

More detailed information at: Multiband photometer CE318-N. User's manual (http://support.cimel.fr/photo/pdf/man_ce318_us.pdf).

Goloub et al., Good practices : [a report on the requirements for SI-traceable calibrations of sunphotometers from aerosol remote sensing monitoring networks. Metrology for Aerosol Optical Properties.](#), 2023

Giles, D. M., Sinyuk, A., Sorokin, M. G., Schafer, J. S., Smirnov, A., Slutsker, I., Eck, T. F., Holben, B. N., Lewis, J. R., Campbell, J. R., Welton, E. J., Korkin, S. V., and Lyapustin, A. I. (2019): Advancements in the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) Version 3 database – automated near-real-time quality control algorithm with improved cloud screening for Sun photometer aerosol optical depth (AOD) measurements, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, **12**, 169-209, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-169-2019>.